

Behaviour of Diazotised Sulphanilamides with Reactive Unsaturated Compounds. Substituted Sulphamidocinnamic Acids

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Diazonium chlorides of sulphanilamidopyrimidines react at pH 1.0 in presence of cupric chloride with acrylonitrile, acrylic ester, crotonic acid, and crotonic ester to furnish α -chloro-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamido-hydrocinnamic acid derivatives which on heating with EtOH-NaOH are converted into *p*-pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic acids. Maleic acid, however, yields α -chloro- β -carboxy-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamido-hydrocinnamic acid at pH 1.0 and *p*-pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic acid at pH 3.0.

Diazonium chlorides of 2-sulphanilamides couple with reactive methylene compounds to form 2-sulphanilamidoazo derivatives¹. It has now been observed that these also react with olefinic compounds under the Meerwein conditions²⁻⁶, resulting in the union of aryl group from the diazonium salt with the carbon atom, β to the activating group, either by substitution of a β -hydrogen atom or by addition of aryl and chlorine to the double bond. Thus maleic acid, when treated with the diazotised solution of sulphanilamidopyrimidine at pH 3.0 and in presence of cupric chloride, yielded *p*-pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic acid (I), whereas at pH 1.0 it furnished α -chloro- β -carboxy-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidohydrocinnamic acid (II). The latter on warming with sodium bicarbonate solution was converted into β -carboxy-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic acid(III).

The structure of compound (I) follows from the fact that it is also obtained when methyl α -chloro-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidohydrocinnamate (IV) and α -chloro-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidohydrocinnamionitrile (V), prepared by treating the diazotised solution of sulphanilamidopyrimidine with the acetonic solution of methyl acrylate and acrylonitrile, respectively, are subjected to hydrolysis and dehydrohalogenation.

Ar. CX: CH.COOH

- (I) : X = H.
 (III) : X = COOH.
 (VII) : X = Me.

Ar. CHX. CHCl.R

- (II) : X = R = COOH.
 (IV) : X = H; R = COOMe
 (V) : X = H; R = -CN
 (VI) : X = Me; R = COOH

1. Prakash and Gambhir, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 847; 1964, 41, 133, 229, 849.
2. Meerwein *et al.*, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, 152, 237.
3. Rai and Mathur, *this Journal*, 1947, 24, 383.
4. Denivelle and Razavi, *Compt. rend.*, 1954, 237, 870.
5. Koelsch, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 57.
6. Koelsch and Boekelheide, *ibid.*, 1944, 66, 412.

Crotonic acid, another $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated acid, when treated with the diazotised solution of sulphanilamidopyrimidine in presence of cupric chloride in aqueous medium, formed α -chloro- β -methyl-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidohydrocinnamic acid (VI). The ethyl ester of crotonic acid, when treated under similar conditions, formed ethyl- α -chloro- β -methyl-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidohydrocinnamate. Both the compounds (VI) and its ester derivative were converted into β -methyl-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic acid (VII) when their ethanolic solutions were heated with sodium acetate and sodium hydroxide, respectively.

Diazotised sulphanilamidodimethylpyrimidine, when similarly treated with $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated compounds, behaved likewise.

EXPERIMENTAL

p-Pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic Acid (I).—The diazotised solution of sulphanilamidopyrimidine (2.65 g.) was added to a solution of maleic acid (1.2 g.) in water (20 ml) containing cupric chloride (0.6 g.) and sodium acetate (2.5 g.); the mixture was stirred throughout, maintaining the temperature at 40°. On keeping it overnight, a brown solid was deposited which was washed with water and extracted with warm 5% sodium bicarbonate solution. The extract on being treated with HCl formed a precipitate which was recrystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 185°, yield 24%. (Found: C, 50.92; H, 3.38. $C_{13}H_{11}O_4N_3S$ requires C, 51.14; H, 3.60%).

α -Chloro- β -carboxy-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidohydrocinnamic Acid (II).—In a similar procedure as above, the diazotised solution of sulphanilamidopyrimidine (2.5 g.) and maleic acid (1.2 g.) at pH 1.0 deposited a yellow solid which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 38% of the acid (II) in yellow needles, m.p. 181°. (Found: C, 43.31; H, 3.00. $C_{14}H_{12}O_6N_3ClS$ requires C, 43.58; H, 3.11%).

β -Carboxy-*p*-pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic Acid (III).—A solution of compound (II) (3.8 g.) in 5% sodium bicarbonate (25 ml) was heated for few minutes. On cooling and acidification with HCl, it formed a precipitate which on recrystallisation from ethanol furnished 80% of the acid (III) in pale yellow prisms, m.p. 196°. (Found: C, 43.01; H, 3.00. $C_{14}H_{11}O_6N_3S$ requires C, 43.13; H, 3.15%).

TABLE I

p-Pyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic acid derivatives.

<i>p</i> -(Pyrimidylsulphamido)-	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
Methyl α -chloro-(.....)-hydrocinnamate (IV)	115°	40%	$C_{14}H_{11}O_4N_3ClS$	C: 46.95 % H: 3.30	47.25 % 3.93
α -Chloro-(.....)-hydrocinnamitrile (V)	127°	40	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_4ClS$	C: 48.04 H: 3.26	48.37 3.41
α -Chloro- β -methyl-(.....)-hydrocinnamic acid (VI)	154°	30	$C_{14}H_{14}O_4N_3ClS$	C: 47.02 H: 3.61	47.25 3.93
Ethyl α -chloro- β -methyl-(.....)hydrocinnamate	184°	38	$C_{16}H_{18}O_4N_3ClS$	C: 49.87 H: 4.33	50.06 4.69
β -Methyl-(.....)cinnamic acid (VII)	204°	60	$C_{14}H_{13}O_4N_3S$	C: 52.41 H: 3.62	52.66 4.07

p-Pyrimidylsulphamido- and *p*-(4, 6-dimethylpyrimidylsulphamido) cinnamic acids and their derivatives were similarly obtained by the reaction of maleic acid, methyl acrylate, acrylonitrile, crotonic acid, etc. with diazotised sulphanilamidopyrimidine and sulphanilamidodimethylpyrimidine (Tables I and II).

TABLE II

4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidylsulphamidocinnamic acid and its derivatives.

<i>p</i> -(4, 6-Dimethylpyrimidylsulphamido)-	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
-Cinnamic acid	212°	20 %	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₄ N ₃ S	C : 53.81% H : 4.22	54.06% 4.50
α-Chloro-β-carboxy-(...) hydrocinnamic acid	225°	38	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ O ₅ N ₃ ClS	C : 46.20 H : 3.68	46.43 3.87
β-Carboxy-(.....)-cinnamic acid	241°	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₃ S	C : 50.69 H : 3.64	50.92 3.97
Methyl α-chloro-(.....)- hydrocinnamate	141°	38	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ ClS	C : 49.82 H : 4.34	50.05 4.60
α-Chloro-(.....)-hydro- cinnamitrile	162°	38	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ ClS	C : 51.17 H : 4.09	51.35 4.27
α-Chloro-β-methyl-(.....)- hydrocinnamic acid	201°	30	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₃ ClS	C : 49.85 H : 4.33	50.06 4.89
Ethyl α-chloro-β-methyl- (.....)-hydrocinnamate	173°	38	C ₁₈ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₃ ClS	C : 52.23 H : 5.16	52.49 5.34
β-Methyl-(.....)- cinnamic acid	221°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₃ S	C : 55.13 H : 4.76	55.30 4.88

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